

Nuclear observations to improve Climate research and GHG
emission estimates

Radon measurements with an ANSTO detector

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As mentioned, we are measuring radon in the air at both Graciosa and Mace Head. For this, we are using ANSTO two-filter dual flow-loop radon detectors. That might sound complicated – and the details, of course, are – but today, we want to explain the concept of these sensors.

The detector maintains a continuous airflow through all its segments at all times. As a first step, before it gets to the main detector, any large particles in the air (e.g. dust, soot or pollen) are removed using a cheap disposable filter, to keep the inside of the pump and detector clean.

ANSTO radon monitor concept

Next, the air moves through a thoron delay volume. Thoron is one isotope of radon (radon-220) that we do not want to measure. It has a half-life of less than one minute. The sampled air takes about 5 minutes to move through the thoron delay volume and during this time almost all thoron (97%) will decay (from a gas to a particle). Once the air reaches the detector, any particle decay products of radon and thoron are removed by the detector’s first filter before the air moves into the detector’s main delay volume. This volume has more than three times the volume of the thoron delay volume. As with the thoron delay, air moves continuously in and out of this volume, but it stays inside for about 20 minutes.

ANSTO radon monitor flow loops

Once the air leaves this volume it is released back into the environment. During the 20 minutes that air is inside this main volume, some of the radon-222

gas will decay to form new particles. All the while, there is a separate pump inside this main volume that guides air very quickly through the detector's measurement head, which catches these new particles. Radon concentration is then determined by counting the decay of these radon progeny particles.

ANSTO radon monitor measurement head

The measurement head contains the detector's second filter. The air from the radon delay volume enters the measurement head and flows through a very fine mesh filter, which captures the newly formed radon progeny. The decay of these progeny is then counted by the detector and used to calculate the amount of radon in the original air. The air moves back into the sample delay volume (this is the second flow loop).

For the detectors we are using, the thoron delay has a volume of 400 L and the sample delay 1500 L, so it needs some space – but the larger the sample delay volume, the more accurate the detector. On the pictures you can see what the set up looks like in reality. One set up on Graciosa and the other one during assembly at Mace Head.

They also have much a much bigger radon monitor as you see on the photo. The large one in the front has a source delay volume of 5000 L and is the largest and most sensitive in the world. It is stationed at Kennaook / Cape Grim Baseline Atmospheric Pollution Station. The 1500 L (in the back) looks small in comparison!

On ANSTO's website are some more information about the detectors and where they are used: <https://www.ansto.gov.au/radon-analytical-facilities>